

Ijarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the mapping of research topics surrounding Ijarah contracts in the Islamic Financial Inclusion with a mix-method approach, namely VOSviewer bibliometric studies and library research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications surrounding the Ijarah agreement; (2) mapping the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization results regarding the Ijarah contract based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) Mapping Research Topics surrounding the Ijarah contract using a library research. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 295 journal publications surrounding the Ijarah agreement; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results surrounding the Ijarah contract are divided into 5 clusters and 125 topic items; (3) based on mapping library research studies, there are 10 The main topic is about the Ijarah contract. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics surrounding the Ijarah contract, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research surrounding the Ijarah contract. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics surrounding the Ijarah contract which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Ijarah; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

In Indonesia, Islamic banks have a fund distribution system in the form of business, profit sharing and contracts. The contract referred to here is the Ijarah Agreement, which is a form of contract to obtain income from goods through sales channels of the benefits of goods or services. Ijarah financing is different from the concept of conventional bank credit, and Ijarah financing is also considered to be a driver of the business sector because of the special nature of ijarah financing compared to other types of sharia financing. There is no transfer of property rights in conventional bank leasing transactions, that is, the property being rented is returned to the owner of the property being rented after the end of the rental period, so a financing service agent is generally not needed. However, Islamic banking practices are different because financing is known to be based on a rental agreement known as Ijarah.

The Ijarah contract is one of the superior products in the Islamic Financial Inclusion, especially sharia banking. An Ijarah contract is also referred to as a rental contract, where within a certain period of time there is a transfer of the right to use a good or service with the payment of rent or wages,

without transferring the right to own a good or service to the lessee. The Islamic Financial Inclusion has a benefit rental financing model and is aimed at financing Umrah, this is also included in the implementation of the Ijarah contract in the Islamic Financial Inclusion including sharia banking.

Scientific research regarding the Ijarah contract has developed over time. Based on scientific research searches, 315 scientific studies were found since 2005, and 35 scientific studies in 2022 that examined the Ijarah contract. This has shown that the Ijarah contract is in great demand in society.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around a card Ijarah in the Islamic Finance Industry in Indonesia by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics around the Ijarah card, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research around the Hawalah card. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around a card Ijarah that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Ijarah contract is an agreement to transfer the right to use (use) a good or service for a certain period of time with payment of rent or wages, without further transferring ownership of the goods themselves, so that in the ijarah contract there is no change in ownership, only the transfer of use rights from the rental transfer to the lessee.

Bibliometric studies are the application of mathematical and statistical methods to study information publications, in this case articles, books, or other information media. The aim of a bibliometric study is to understand the development of literature in the field of information or science publishing. VOSviewer is software that can be used to build, explore and visualize bibliometric networks such as journals, articles, authors, authors, titles, publications, etc. In addition, VOSviewer is capable of mapping various types of bibliometric analysis, complex visualization with visual labels, and the creation of primary bibliographic databases.

A library research is a general overview that contains a description of theories, findings and other relevant research materials obtained from reference sources to be used as a basis for research activities. This library research aims to establish a clear framework for thinking and problem solving as explained in the previous problem formulation.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research studies. The object of the research is the Ijarah contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about the Ijarah contract in the Sharia Finance Industry.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and

Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word “Ijarah” within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Ijarah contracts using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around Ijarah contracts using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) Mapping Research Topics surrounding the Ijarah contract using a library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Ijarah Agreements in the Islamic Financial Inclusion

There are 295 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 20 05 to 202 2. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding A card Ijarah by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2005	1	2013	9	2018	33
2008	1	2014	5	2019	27
2009	1	2015	13	2020	47
2010	2	2016	9	2021	40
2012	3	2017	26	2022	86

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

Mapping Research Topics Regarding the Ijarah Agreement in the Islamic Financial Inclusion using the VOSviewer Bibliometric Study

Search results on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba) regarding Ijarah card research articles are downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) format then input and analyzed using the VOSViewer device. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments surrounding the Ijarah Agreement

1. Its application is in the agricultural, fisheries and plantation sectors. The findings in this case are: first, the implementation of the Ijarah A'mal agreement Musyarakah is not suitable to be applied in the case of agricultural workers, because it does not fulfill the requirements of the Ijarah contract; second, Ijarah Multijasa financing for re-planting oil palm plantations at PT. Bank Muamalat Indonesia KC Padang is not in accordance with the principles of the Ijarah contract because the wage/ujrah system is still in the form of a percentage, even though it should be nominal; third, from the farmer's side, it can improve their lives; fourth, in the plantation sector, the ijarah agreement in Denok village, Lumajang district, is in accordance with the legal principles of muamalat jurisprudence which is based on the principles of justice, permissibility, consent, benefit and custom which are the basis of the law, fifth, in the fisheries sector, the Ijarah agreement in Banjarpanji Village is in progress in accordance with the legal principles of muamalah fiqh and improving the welfare of life.
2. Application in the Sharia Finance Industry. The findings of this research are: first, several LKS did not implement the Ijarah contract correctly in accordance with the characteristics of the Ijarah contract; second, several sharia leasing companies have not implemented Ijarah contracts in accordance with DSN-MUI provisions; third, the Ijarah Benefit Lease Financing Agreement implemented by LKS No. 10669/IJR/IX/2012 in accordance with the DSN-MUI fatwa regarding financing with Ijarah contracts; fourth, the marketing strategy for Ijarah financing is less than optimal at BMT Al Fataya Payakumbuh; fifth, rental fees may not be determined based on the nominal amount of the loan, but there is a fixed nominal rental fee, or only making a profit from rental fees for storage space if in the sharia pawnshop industry.
3. Its application to land management. The findings in this case are: first, the Ijarah contract carried out is in accordance with sharia principles; second, the use of village land to build regional/people's markets.
4. Application to gold financing products. The findings in this case are: first, when the financing is due, the customer pays a rental fee for storing gold throughout the rental period; second, banks must do so carefully and in accordance with sharia principles; third, the bank does not provide excess or excess funds in the financing funds provided to customers; fourth, vulnerable to manipulative irregularities in the contract; fifth, determining rental fees must be based on the actual costs incurred for maintenance, not based on the target amount to be achieved.
5. Its application to Hajj bailout products. The findings in this case are: first, the bank takes advantage of customers by getting wages/ujrah in accordance with sharia principles if there is a fixed nominal amount, not based on a percentage of the bailout amount; secondly, the combination of qardh and ijarah contracts in this product is not in accordance with fatwa no. 29/DSN- MUI/VI/2002 concerning financing for Hajj arrangements; third, there is no role for a notary in making a financing agreement deed, even though in Article 1 paragraph 1 of Law no. 2 of 2014 states that an authentic deed is made by a notary, this is because this deed is made privately by the bank; fourth, besides bringing benefits, there are also risks in this product, including that this product will include people who are not financially ready to register for the Hajj quota, so this will lengthen the queue for Hajj departures; fifth, obstacles in

implementing this product, including customers who are prospective Hajj pilgrims dying before their departure time, customers being unable to pay off the bailout funds lent by the bank, lack of support from community leaders and there are still pros and cons regarding this product.

6. Its application to multiservice financing. The findings in this case are: first, fatwa no. 44/DSN-MUI/VIII/2004 concerning multiservice financing; secondly, the financing mechanism is not complicated, so it is one of the factors that attracts people's interest in using this financing; third, this agreement is very effective in improving undergraduate education; fourth, baby equipment rental; fifth, Umrah financing has been carried out in accordance with sharia principles based on the DSN-MUI fatwa; sixth, other types of financing, namely in the fields of health, marriage, employment and tourism; seventh, there is the potential for irregularities in this financing product, because the wage profits provided are adjusted to the amount of bailout funds provided, so there is potential for usury in it; seventh, determining rental wages based on the percentage of the financing ceiling violates the DSN-MUI fatwa, which requires rental wages to be in nominal form; eighth, sometimes the LKS does not do anything when a customer applies for multiservice financing, but it seems as if the LKS only gives a certain amount of money to the customer and then there is a wage/ujrah requirement for borrowing funds from the LKS, which is not in accordance with the DSN-fatwa MUI regarding multiservice financing mechanisms.
7. Its application to BUMDes financing. The findings in this case are: implementation is effective, although there are several obstacles, such as still using a manual system, less efficient financing distribution and minimal public understanding of the Ijarah contract.
8. Application to society. The findings in this case are: first, there were several unhealthy Ijarah contract transactions, for example the owner unilaterally canceled the existing Ijarah contract because there was an offer of a higher rental fee for various reasons; second, the Ijarah contract system in the majority of boarding houses is in accordance with sharia principles; third, its application to the sharia business run by the Sumenep Muhammadiyah orphanage, even though there are several shortcomings, both in terms of business capital and human resources; fourth, its implementation in the salary system for teachers and education personnel in schools, even though there are shortcomings based on the principle of the Ijarah contract in Islamic sharia; fifth, its application to wages given to builders; sixth, due to the many problems in society regarding the Ijarah agreement, it is recommended that the transaction be written down on paper or have a witness present, so that if one day a problem occurs, they can refer to the agreement letter; seventh, the practice of rice irrigation services is that sometimes contracts occur verbally and in mutual trust, there is no written recording, but it is difficult to mitigate a problem if a violation arises in the contract.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of the Ijarah Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 5 research topics regarding the influence of the Ijarah contract, namely:

1. Its influence on the profitability of the Islamic Financial Inclusion, in the form of Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Assets/ROA and ROF. The findings in this case are: first, Ijarah financing has a significant effect on ROE, ROA and ROF; second, rental rates for pawned goods do not have a significant effect on ROE; third, Ijarah financing does not have a significant effect on net profit; fourth, the Ijarah variable does not have a significant effect on BUS profitability because the amount of financing is small compared to other financing, such as Mudharabah, Murabahah and Musyarakah; fifth, Ijarah income has a significant effect on Return On Assets/ROA.
2. The impact on MSMEs. The findings in this case are: first, the Ijarah contract product has a significant effect on increasing MSME business income; second, financing with an Ijarah agreement is good for developing MSME businesses in the long term, compared to Mudharabah and Murabahah contracts; third, MSME players get business capital quickly.
3. Its influence on company value. The findings in this case are: Ijarah financing does not have a significant effect on the company value of the Islamic banking sector.
4. Its influence on the company's health level. The findings in this case are: Ijarah financing has a significant effect on the company's health level.
5. Its effect on the company's total assets. The findings in this case are: Ijarah financing has a significant effect on the company's total assets.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Juridical Studies on Ijarah Contracts

In this sub-chapter, there are 7 research topics regarding juridical studies of Ijarah contracts, namely:

1. The Ijarah contract is based on the Koran and Hadith. The findings in this case are: first, Surah Al-Qashshah verses 26-27; second, Surah Al-Thalaq verse 6; third, Surah Al-Zukhruf verse 32; fourth, the hadith narrated by 'Abd Al-Razzaq from Abu Sa'id Al-Khudriy and Abu Hurairah in the book Musnad Ahmad: " Whoever employs workers, must be informed of the amount of his wages "; fifth, hadith narrated by Ibnu Umar in Sunan Ibnu Majah: " Give ujarah to workers before their sweat dries "; sixth, hadith narrated by Sa'd bin Abi Waqqash in Sunan Abi Dawud: " We once rented out land with wages in the form of agricultural products, then the Messenger of Allah sallallahu 'Alaihi Wasallam forbade this and ordered us to rent it out for wages in gold or silver "; seventh, the rules of jurisprudence which originate from the ulama's consensus regarding the Ijarah contract: " The original law of muamalat is permissibility, unless there is an argument that forbids it " and " Preventing damage takes precedence over bringing benefit."
2. The Ijarah agreement is based on the DSN-MUI fatwa. The findings in this case are: first, Fatwa no. 9/DSN-MUI/VI/2000 concerning Ijarah; second, Fatwa no. 27/DSN-MUI/III/2002 concerning IMBT; third, Fatwa no. 101-102/DSN-MUI/X/2016 concerning the Ijarah Maushufah fi Dzimmah agreement; fourth, Fatwa no. 112/DSN-MUI/IX/2017 concerning the Ijarah contract; fifth, Fatwa no. 44/DSN-MUI/IV/2004 concerning Ijarah Multijasa financing.

3. The Ijarah contract is based on Islamic law and positive law. The findings in this case are: first, the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) in Chapter X, Articles 251-290 regarding the Ijarah contract; second, Law no. 3 of 2006 concerning the authority of the Religious Courts to resolve cases in the field of sharia banking.
4. Accounting for Ijarah contracts. The findings in this case are: first, PSAK No. 107 in Indonesia; second, the Financial Accounting Standard (FAS 8) which was developed by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) internationally; third, the use of the Malaysian Accounting Standard Board (MASB 10) in Malaysia; fourth, indicators in PSAK No. 107, namely definitions, characteristics, lessor accounting, lessee accounting, advanced ijarah, presentation and disclosure; fifth, in practice, banks should carry out 2 types of accounting, either as lessor or lessee, sixth, the accounting treatment for Ijarah financing at KSPPS BMT Arma has been carried out in accordance with sharia principles; seventh, International Accounting Standard on Leasing (IAS 17) which was developed by International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS).
5. Default on Ijarah contract in the decision of the high religious court. The findings in this case are: first, the judge's consideration in the decision of the case regarding default on Ijarah contract number 0223/Pdt.G/2015/PTA.Sby is in accordance with KHES and the applicable law; secondly, resolution of default cases in sharia banking can be done through mediation or the National Sharia Arbitration Board of the Indonesian Ulema Council (BASYARNAS-MUI).
6. The Ijarah contract is based on fiqh law. The findings in this case are: first, understanding, legal basis, pillars, conditions, objects, types, rental period, philosophy of realizing the principles of monotheism and justice, contract implementation, risk bearing, legal consequences, asset maintenance, determination of rental fees, guarantees/collateral, obligations of the party carrying out the contract, implications of deletion/amendment of the contract, failure to pay overdue rental fees, use of contemporary ijarah, conventional hire-purchase contracts, merging two contracts, Islamic banker guidelines in Ijarah contracts, moral values in contracts Ijarah; second, the end of the Ijarah contract if there is damage to the rental object, the death of one of the parties to the transaction and the final goal of the contract has been achieved.
7. The Ijarah contract is based on maqashid sharia. The findings in this case are: first, the indicator of maintaining religion/hifzhu din, there is a charity in the form of alms in the implementation of the contract, second, the indicator of maintaining the soul/hifzhu nafs, there is the ability to meet life's needs; third, the indicator of safeguarding reason/hifzhu 'aql, there is an increase in knowledge in the Ijarah contract, fourth, the indicator of safeguarding offspring/hifzhu nasl, there is the ability to improve the education of children and descendants; fifth, the indicator of protecting property/hifzhu mall, there is an increase in income for object owners, and business opportunities for tenants.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Ijarah Contract Development Efforts

In this sub-chapter, there are 9 research topics surrounding efforts to develop the Ijarah contract, namely:

1. Ijarah Maushufah fi Dzimmah (IMFD) agreement. The findings in this case are: first, this contract is a development of a contract based on monotheism; second, the difference with the special Ijarah agreement, Salam and Istishna'; third, applied in financing home ownership/indent mortgages, education, infrastructure and sukuk; fourth, to become a financing solution in the Islamic Financial Inclusion; fifth, the Go-Pay application complies with sharia principles by using the Ijarah Maushufah fi Zimmah (IMFZ) agreement.
2. Mutanaqishah Ijarah Agreement. The findings in this case are: this contract really helped Nazir in obtaining capital from an investor for the costs of empowering the waqf land.
3. Rahn products have an Ijarah agreement in sharia pawning. The findings in this case are: first, the transaction is not in accordance with sharia principles, because the Ijarah contract is renting out benefits, not a transfer of ownership of assets; second, the Ijarah rate changes according to the amount of loan given; third, there is a discount on the Ijarah contract.
4. Waqf is based on an Ijarah agreement. The findings in this case are: economic empowerment of village communities can take the form of empowering waqf assets with an ijarah agreement. There is a need for management and nazhir to make these waqf assets effective. For example, someone donates waqf land which is built on a rented house/shophouse, then the proceeds are earmarked for the operation of mosques and orphanages in the surrounding area.
5. Development of Ijarah agreement based on SWOT analysis. The findings in this case are: first, strength includes margin/profit and profit sharing, able to compete with conventional bank products, easy requirements, contracts in accordance with sharia principles, fast financing process; secondly, weaknesses/weaknesses include a lack of socialization to the public regarding contracts, the public's opinion that there is no difference in the products issued by sharia banks and conventional banks, inadequate human resources; third, opportunities include public interest which is starting to increase in sharia banking products so that they must be provided with the best service; fourth, threats include the many product innovations offered by conventional banks, as well as the low level of public literacy regarding the advantages of sharia banking products.
6. Development of Ijarah contracts in the sharia capital market. The findings in this case are: Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik (IMBT), Ijarah Maushufah Fi Zimmah (IMFZ), State Sukuk/Sukuk Ijarah SBSN (State Sharia Securities and Ijarah Sukuk).
7. Development of Ijarah contracts in digital money/cryptomining. The findings in this case are: mining activities were carried out according to the principles of the Ijarah contract, but there was confusion in the payment of rental wages using foreign currency. This confusion occurs because the payment of wages is not in cash/on the spot, but there needs to be a time lag until the wages are sent to those entitled to them.
8. Ijarah contract marketing strategy. The findings in this case are: first, products with the development/innovation of sharia financial products; second, price/price; third, place; fourth, promotion by intensive

advertising; fifth, process/process; sixth, physical evidence/physical appearance; and seventh, people with personal selling directly to consumers to provide knowledge of sharia products.

9. Information system in Ijarah contract transactions. The findings in this case are: first, this is to reduce problems that occur due to incomplete customer data and the availability of effective information, second, its application to sharia hotels in Bandung.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence the Ijarah Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 4 Research topics revolve around the factors that influence the Ijarah contract, namely:

1. Factors that cause damage to Ijarah contracts in Islamic banks. The findings in this case are: first, the customer removed/obliterated the rental object; second, customers are unable to pay their obligations because they have a lot of debt in other financial industries; third, customers' incomes decrease, they even get fired from their jobs; fourth, the customer provides incorrect information or documents to the sharia bank.
2. Factors that influence the reluctance of banks and the public to use Ijarah contracts are: the existence of additional taxes, namely Value Added Tax (VAT), so that it becomes a burden. This has an impact on the low level of interest in Ijarah contracts in sharia bank financing transactions.
3. Financial Deposit Ratio (FDR). The findings in this case are: FDR had a significant effect on Ijarah financing.
4. Operating Expenses to Operating Income (BOPO). The findings in this case are: BOPO does not have a significant effect on Ijarah financing.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence Community Interest in the Ijarah Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 4 The research topic revolves around the factors that influence people's interest in the Ijarah contract, namely:

1. Sharia principles, ujarah/wages and services. The findings of these factors are: all three have a simultaneous and significant effect on people's interest in using the Ijarah contract.
2. Awareness, perception, religiosity, income and comfort. The findings of these factors are: all five have a simultaneous and significant effect on people's interest in using the Ijarah contract.
3. Ijarah Rates. The findings in this factor are: Ijarah rates have a significant effect on people's interest in Ijarah contracts.
4. Ijarah Agreement. The findings in this factor are: the Ijarah contract has a significant effect on people's interest in the Ijarah contract.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Sukuk Ijarah

In this sub-chapter, there are 9 research topics regarding the implementation of the Ijarah contract in Sukuk, namely:

1. Issuance of Sukuk Ijarah in juridical studies. The findings in this case are: first, Law no. 19 of 2008 concerning State Sharia Securities (SBSN);

second, Financial Services Authority Regulation no. 18/POJK.004/2015 concerning issuance and requirements for sukuk; third, fatwa no. 09/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Ijarah financing; fourth, fatwa no. 72/DSN-MUI/2008 concerning National Sharia Securities (SBSN) Ijarah Sale and Lease Bank; fifth, fatwa no. 69/DSN-MUI/VI/2008 concerning National Sharia Securities (SBSN)/State Sukuk.

2. Causes of failure to pay Ijarah sukuk. The findings in this case are: first, the existence of an interest system in the Sukuk Ijarah; second, the use of collected funds to pay company debts, not for productive businesses.
3. Comparison of the performance of conventional bonds and Ijarah sukuk. The findings in this case are: based on nominal yield, current yield, realized yield and yield to maturity, there is no significant difference in performance between the two, but it can be assessed that Ijarah sukuk have better performance than conventional bonds.
4. Accounting treatment of Ijarah sukuk. The findings in this case are: overall, the accounting treatment is in accordance with PSAK 110.
5. The advantages of Ijarah sukuk compared to others. The findings in this case are: Ijarah sukuk are more popular with the public because they provide fixed wages/fixed fees than Mudharabah Sukuk which provide variable profit sharing or in accordance with the profit sharing ratio.
6. Issuance of Ijarah sukuk in other countries. The findings in this case are: first, this sukuk was also issued in non-Muslim countries, such as Germany, Japan and China; second, the issuance of Ijarah sukuk in Nigeria aims to improve the people's economy, sources of financing and liquidity from the private sector.
7. Its application to the infrastructure sector. The findings in this case are: first, Ijarah sukuk can be an alternative financing in the infrastructure sector; secondly, there needs to be a fatwa from the DSN-MUI that strengthens the use of Ijarah sukuk.
8. Value at Risk (VaR) of Ijarah sukuk. The findings in this case are: Ijarah Sukuk have smaller risks than Mudharabah Sukuk.
9. Effect of Ijarah Sukuk. The findings in this case are: first, Sukuk Ijarah has a significant effect on Return On Assets/ROA, Economic Value Added/EVA, Price Earning Ratio/PER and Price to Book Value/PBV; secondly, Sukuk Ijarah does not have a significant effect on Return On Equity (ROE) and Earning Per Share/EPS.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence Sukuk Ijarah

In this sub-chapter, there are 5 research topics surrounding the factors that influence Sukuk Ijarah, namely:

1. Revision of PSAK 110 on Sharia Capital Markets. The findings in this case are: there is no difference in the value of sukuk even though there is a revision of PSAK 110.
2. Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. The findings in this case are: significant effect on Ijarah sukuk returns.
3. Return On Assets/ROA, inflation and SBI interest rates. The findings in this case are: both do not have a significant effect on Ijarah sukuk returns.

4. Bond maturity, Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), expense coverage ratio, Net Profit Margin/NPM and liquidity ratio. The findings in this case are: all four have a significant effect on the Ijarah sukuk rental rate.
5. Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Return On Equity/ROE, Gross Profit Margin/GPM, company size, profitability ratio, bond maturity and activity ratio. The findings in this case are: the six of them do not have a significant effect on the Ijarah sukuk rental rate.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Implementation of the Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik (IMBT) Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 14 research topics regarding the implementation of the Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik agreement, namely:

1. The IMBT contract is based on the Koran and Hadith. The findings in this case are: first, Surah Al-Baqarah verse 233; second, Surah Al-Qashash verse 26; third, Surah Al-Kahf verse 77; fourth, the arguments of hadith and ijma' are included in the sub-chapter of juridical studies regarding the Ijarah contract.
2. The IMBT contract is based on juridical studies. The findings in this case are: first, National Sharia Council fatwa no. 27/DSN-MUI/III/2002; second, Law no. 10 of 1998; third, Law no. 21 of 2008; fourth, PBI No. 9/19/PBI/2007; fifth, Decree of the Chairman of Bapepam and LK Number: PER-04/BL/2007; sixth, Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) Articles 251-290; seventh, Civil Code Articles 1319, 1320 and 1338; eighth, SEBI No. 5/26/BPS/2003 Pg. 111; ninth, PBI No. 10/17/PBI/2008 dated 25 September 2008; tenth, SEBI Appendix No. 10/31/DPBS dated 7 October 2008; eleventh, SEBI No. 10/14/DPBS dated 17 March 2008; twelfth, PBI No. 7/46/PBI/2005 Article 16; thirteenth, IMBT's accounting treatment is based on the provisions of PSAK 107.
3. IMBT contracts according to classical and contemporary muamalah fiqh. The findings in this case are: first, understanding, pillars, conditions, legal basis, characteristics, mechanisms, transfer of ownership, benefits and risks of IMBT financing contracts; second, the IMBT concept; third, implementation and case examples of IMBT; fourth, problems in the IMBT contract; fifth, the difference between leasing and Murabahah and IMBT; sixth, the advantages and disadvantages of the IMBT contract.
4. IMBT contract according to Islamic figures. The findings in this case are: first, the implementation of the IMBT contract in the Islamic Financial Inclusion in Indonesia is in accordance with sharia principles based on the concept of maqashid tasarrufat maliyyah, the idea of Ibn Asyur; secondly, according to Sarah bint Adil bin Muhammad Amin Rauzi divides IMBT into 5, namely: Ijariyah, Ramziy, Haqiqiy, Bai' and Grant.
5. IMBT Agreement in the Sharia and Non-Islamic Financial Inclusion. The findings in this case are: first, in the transaction process there are several stages that must be passed. Second, the financing agreement is in accordance with sharia principles; third, the Sharia Finance Industry can become the holder of mortgage rights in IMBT contract financing; fourth, the application of this agreement in non-shariah industries is considered to be in accordance with sharia principles, although improvements are needed; fifth, this contract is still rarely used by LKS in fund distribution products due to lack of public literacy and knowledge; sixth, the IMBT

- contract not only emphasizes profits, but also the principle of justice; seventh, there is an insurance clause in the IMBT contract as a way to protect the contracting party from damage to the object of the contract.
6. IMBT agreement in KPR products. The findings in this case are: first, the implementation of the IMBT contract is in accordance with sharia principles; secondly, there is the implementation of an inverted pyramid installment system, where the principal installments are fixed each month, but the margin becomes smaller and smaller over time; thirdly, there is confusion in this contract regarding the guarantee of a house where the house is not fully owned by the customer, even though this is not legal according to sharia, but is legal according to positive law in Indonesia.
 7. Comparison of the IMBT contract with other contracts. The findings of this research are: first, the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah (MMQ) contract is more popular with the Sharia Finance Industry because the mechanism is easy and can be used for all forms of financing; secondly, Murabahah contracts are more popular because the process is easier and the installments are fixed until the end of the payment period; third, the hire-purchase contract does not have permanent legal certainty, so that when a dispute occurs, it even has the potential to violate Article 18 of the Consumer Protection Law.
 8. Factors of customer interest in IMBT contract financing. The findings in this case are: social media promotion, BI equivalent rate, Halal Awareness, financial literacy, trust and service.
 9. Factors decreasing customer interest in choosing IMBT financing. The findings in this case are: first, customers get a smaller financing value if they use the IMBT contract; second, changes in financing installments at any time, resulting in uncertainty among customers; third, most customers do not know about the products produced by the IMBT contract because the company places restrictions on marketing these products.
 10. Calculation of income tax for IMBT contracts. The findings in this case are: there are multiple interpretations of Financial Metrics Regulation no. 136 & 137/PMK.03/2011 concerning the Imposition of Income Tax for sharia financing transaction activities, so it is necessary to provide legal training so that there are no more multiple interpretations for Account Representatives (AR).
 11. Implication of promise (wa'd) in IMBT transactions. The findings in this case are: first, fatwa no. 85/DSN -MUI/on the IMBT contract; secondly, there is clarity in resolving disputes between parties, both through litigation and through the Alternative Dispute Resolution Industry.
 12. IMBT contract in the community. The findings in this case are: this contract can be a solution to improve the economy of the people/society.
 13. Bad credit on the IMBT contract. The findings in this case are: based on the decision of the religious court no. 554/Pdt.G/2018/PA.Pal is in accordance with the DSN-MUI and KHES fatwa.
 14. Project assessment with IMBT financing. The findings in this case are: the IMBT contract is suitable for project financing because the project assessment parameters have a Net Present Value (NPV) of more than zero, but it is smaller when compared to conventional financing. Thus, conventional financing is more attractive than sharia financing (IMBT).

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Issues Related to the Ijarah Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 6 research topics surrounding other issues related to the Ijarah contract, namely:

1. Comparison of the Ijarah contract with other contracts. The findings in this case are: there are similarities and differences between ijarah and leasing in several ways, namely: the object being rented, payment method, transfer of ownership, variation model (lease-purchase) and sale and lease-back.
2. Sharia Compliance in the Ijarah Agreement. The findings in this case are: first, there are administrative costs not based on the actual/real value but based on the value of the loan and rental object; secondly, the costs of maintaining the rental object are in the hands of the lessee; third, the ownership transfer agreement in the IMBT contract is still ambiguous, whether binding or non-binding; fourth, the amount of compensation or fines due to late payment; fifth, the amount of rental/ujrah fees expressed in percentage, not nominal; sixth, it can give rise to buying and selling transactions that are prohibited by sharia, such as bai' inah, wafa' and ta'alluq; seventh, the possibility of errors in the practice of executing collateral.
3. Problematic financing management in Ijarah contracts. The findings in this case are: first, the sharia bank held discussions with the customer; second, sharia banks apply fines to customers; third, sharia banks carry out financing restructuring; fourth, if the customer is still unable to continue, then the collateral assets will be confiscated.
4. Factors that cause financing problems in Ijarah contracts. The findings in this case are: first, LKS was negligent in identifying the party being financed; second, lack of honesty on the part of the party being financed.
5. Ijarah contract risk management. The findings in this case are: first, LKS has implemented Regulation no. 13/23/PBI/2011 in appropriate risk management mechanisms; secondly, the Pilar Mandiri Syariah Cooperative Surabaya carries out an identification process, assessing the magnitude of the risks to be faced and preparing risk mitigation.
6. Covid-19 pandemic period. The findings in this case are: Ijarah financing has decreased due to the decline in public interest in carrying out Ijarah financing during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Ijarah contracts in the Sharia Finance Industry during the period 2005 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 295 published journal articles. Second, based on Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer bibliometric studies, the results of network visualization around Ijarah contracts in the Sharia Finance Industry are divided into 5 clusters and 125 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 68 topics, cluster 2 consists of 44 topics, cluster 3 consists of 10 topics, cluster 4 consists of 2 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 1 topic. Third, based on Mapping Research Topics using library research studies, there are 10 topics related to Ijarah contracts in the Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Implementation of the Ijarah

Agreement; (2) Influence of the Ijarah Agreement; (3) Juridical Study of the Ijarah Agreement; (4) Efforts to develop the Ijarah Agreement; (5) Factors that Influence the Ijarah Agreement; (6) Factors that Influence Community Interest in the Ijarah Agreement; (7) Ijarah Sukuk; (8) Factors Affecting Sukuk Ijarah; (9) Implementation of the Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik (IMBT) Agreement; and (10) Other issues related to the Ijarah Agreement.

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